

JAVASCRIPT FUNKSIYA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7937125>

Anotatsiya: Bu tezisda JavaScript funksiyalarining asosiy xususiyatlari, ularni yaratish va ishlatish usullari ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, funksiya, sintaksis, parametr, qiymat qaytarish, boshqarish.

Abstract: This thesis shows the main features of JavaScript functions, how to create and use them.

Keywords: JavaScript, function, syntax, parameter, return value, control.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida funksiya, dastur to'plamida yana-qanaqa qayta ishlatiladigan vazifalarni bajarish uchun yoziladi. Funksiyalar o'z ichiga turli xil ma'lumotlar olishi mumkin va o'zgartirishi mumkin. Bu xususiyatlar funksiya yozishni tizimlashga va uni dastur qilishni osonlashtiradi.

Funksiyalarning sintaksisi quyidagicha:

```
function functionName(parameters) {  
  // code to be executed  
  return value;  
}
```

Bu sintaksisda, functionName funksiya nomini va parameters funksiyaga kiritiladigan parametrlarni ifodalaydi. code to be executed esa funksiyani bajaruvchi kodni ifodalaydi. return kalit so'zi esa funksiyadan qiymat qaytarish uchun ishlatiladi.

Funksiyalarni boshqarish quyidagi usullar bilan amalga oshiriladi:

1. Funksiyani chaqirish.
2. Funksiyaga parametrlar uzatish.
3. Funksiyadan qiymat qaytarish.
4. Funksiyani bir o'zgaruvchiga tenglash.

Funksiyalar ko'p xil shakllarda ishlatiladi, masalan:

1. Named functions: Bu funksiyalarni nomlab nomlash mumkin.
2. Anonymous functions: Bu funksiyalar nomsiz yoziladi.
3. Arrow functions: Bu funksiyalar ES6da kiritilgan yangi sintaksisdir.

Funksiyalar ko'p joyda ishlatiladi, masalan:

1. Kichik miqdorda kodlarni qayta ishlash uchun.
2. Foydali funksiyalarni yaratish uchun.
3. Dasturlash tilida ma'lumotlar tahlil qilish uchun.
4. Qo'shimcha dasturlar yaratish uchun.

JavaScript funksiyalari dastur to'plamida ko'plab vazifalarni bajarish uchun yaratilgan. Bu funksiyalar tizimlashni osonlashtiradi va o'zgartirishlarga qulaydir. Funksiyalarni yaratish va ulardan foydalanish JavaScript dasturlash tilida eng muhim qismlardan biri hisoblanadi. JavaScript funksiyalari, o'zgaruvchilar, massivlar va obyektlar bilan birlikda ishlatilishi bilan juda kuchli va qulaydir. Funksiyalarni yaratish uchun, funksiya nomi va argumentlar belgilanadi. Funksiya nomi, funksiyani chaqirish uchun kerak bo'ladigan unikal identifikator

hisoblanadi. Argumentlar esa, funksiyaga kiritilgan ma'lumotlar vaqti kelgan paytda funksiyada ishlatiladi. JavaScript funksiyalari, "function" kalit so'zi va funksiya nomi bilan boshlanadi. Quyidagi misol funksiya nomi "greet" bo'lgan oddiy bir funksiyani yaratish haqida ko'rsatilgan:

```
function greet(name) {  
  console.log("Salom, " + name + "!");  
}
```

Bu funksiya, nomi "greet" bo'lgan va argument sifatida "name" nomli o'zgaruvchini qabul qiladi. Funksiyaga ma'lumotlar kiritish uchun "greet" funksiyasini chaqirish mumkin, masalan:

```
greet("Ali");
```

Bu "greet" funksiyasining chaqirilishiga qarab, "Salom, Ali!" xabari konsolga chiqadi. JavaScript funksiyalari, bir necha usullarda yaratilishi mumkin. Anonim funksiyalar, belgilangan funksiyalar, o'zini chaqiruvchi funksiyalar kabi. Tezida JavaScript funksiyalari va ularning yaratilishi, chaqirilishi, argumentlar, qaytish qiymatlari va boshqa xususiyatlari haqida qisqa ma'lumotlar ko'rsatilgan.

Xulosa

JavaScript funksiyalari dastur to'plamida ko'p vazifalarni bajarish uchun yaratilgan va dastur tizimlashini osonlashtiradi. Funksiyalar dasturlash tilida muhim qismlardan biridir va ulardan foydalanish muhimdir.

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